

**17th Central European Lung Cancer Conference
including
Best of WCLC 2018**

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Dear colleagues,

It is our pleasure to welcome you to the 17th Central European Lung Cancer Conference including Best of WCLC 2018. The Conference is organized by Institute for Pulmonary Diseases in Sremska Kamenica and Central European Lung Cancer Association – CELCA.

The aim of CELCC is to develop strategies for decreasing the burden of lung cancer in Europe. Therefore, we invite different specialists working in the field of lung cancer to participate at the CELCC 2018.

Thank you for your highly appreciated contribution to this Conference.

We wish you a pleasant and rewarding stay in Novi Sad!

On behalf of the Organizing Committee, sincerely,

Prof. Dr Ilija Andrijević
Conference President

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Prof. Dr Robert Pirker
Member of the Board CELCA

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LONG-TERM SURVIVOR NSCLC – CASE REPORT

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Introduction: Lung cancer is the most often diagnosed cancer type worldwide, and at the same time it is the most common cause of deaths among all cancer types.

Case report: In this paper we are presenting the case of a long-term patient in the initially fourth stage of the disease, who has been treated with four lines of chemotherapy. It is about male patient, 61 years old, current smoker, with bronchoscopically confirmed stage IV (cT3N2M1a) squamous cell lung carcinoma of the right lung. First line chemotherapy (HT) with Cisplatin/Gemcitabine was completed, with accomplished partial response. Ten months later radiological disease progression in the lung was observed as an increase of size of the primary tumor (T3N2M1a). Patient had a good performance status, ECOG 1, and the treatment was carried out with 4 cycles second line HT, Cisplatin/Vinorelbine. After second line HT completion, stable disease was confirmed. New progression of the disease in terms of tumor size enlargement (T3N2M1a) was noted 6 months after second line HT completion. The patients still had good performance status, so we continued treatment with third line HT, Carboplatin/ Etoposide in 4 cycles. After 10 months of radiological stable disease, further radiological disease progression was detected as a new metastatic lesion located in right kidney and increasing the size of primary lung tumor (T4N2M1c). Since the patient was still in good condition, treatment was continued with the fourth line HT with Gemcitabin/Carboplatin in 4 cycles, and the treatment is still ongoing. After almost 4 years of diagnosis, the patient is still alive, the treatment is ongoing and has a good quality of life.

Conclusion: We can say that the chemotherapy prolong survival in patients with NSCLC and should be used as standard therapy in patients who have good performance status.

KEYWORDS: chemotherapy, lung cancer, survival

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